

Automatic Lung Cancer Detection in Low-Dose Lung CTs Using Transfer Learning

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Abstract--- Early diagnosis of lung cancer is essential to increase the survival rate of the patients. Manual diagnosis practices are inefficient and time consuming. Subsequently the undetected cases are ended at high risk incurable stage. In this paper a transfer learning based feed-forward Deep Neural Network (DNN) is proposed to detect lung cancer in various stages. This proposed model assists the radiologists in diagnosing lung cancer at the earlier stage and positively reduce the risk of missing cancer. Transfer learning approach improves the performance of deep medical image classification model, where the data is limited. Low dose chest CT scan images from LIDC-IRDI dataset are used for training and evaluating the proposed deep convolutional model. The performance of the proposed model is measured with accuracy, precision, recall and f -measure. The experimental results prove that, the proposed method gives an accuracy of 93.67% on lung cancer detection. The proposed method gives an improved result in terms of accuracy compared with other deep convolutional methods based on VGG16 model.

Keywords--- Lung Cancer Detection, Transfer Learning, Deep Learning, Convolutional Neural Network.

I. Introduction

Low Dose Computed Tomography (LDCT) significantly improves the survival rate of patients at high risk of cancer by means of timely detection, provided the patients are cared with appropriate treatments. Due to the advancement in medical imaging techniques, there is a significant growth in development of computer aided system for diagnosing lung cancer. The objective of developing computer aided diagnosis (CAD) system is to decrease the death rate of lung cancer patients by detecting the disease at its early stage.

Several CADs have been developed to support the radiologists and afford an improvement in detecting cancer with minimum cost. The computer aided system can effectively predict or diagnose the diseases more accurately. Suzuki et al.[1] have proposed a Massive Training Artificial Neural Network (MTANN) for automatic detection of lung nodules directly from the whole CT image data. The MTANN is trained with small patches extracted from the image and learned to distinguish nodule and non-nodule from an input image. After continual training, the model could learn the features needed for classification and become an expert in distinguishing the nodules.

Various models based on supervised machine learning approach have been proposed for diagnosing the diseases with wide range of features directly extracted from the target imaging modality. Three different approaches are used for extracting the features such as: voxel-based approach, Region of Interest (ROI)-based approach and patch-based approach. All these approaches automatically extract the representative features from an image for diagnosis. Patch-based method extracts low level features and the other two approaches extract middle level features. But the clinical diagnosis system requires high level features for better understanding. Recently, many researchers have been working in the field of medical image analysis using deep learning and also achieved promising results. Suk et al. [2] have proposed a high-level latent and shared feature representation for medical imaging modalities with Deep Boltzmann Machine (DBM) for diagnosis. This method outperforms the other traditional methods and achieves a maximal accuracy.

Guorong et al. [3] have proposed an unsupervised deep learning approach to learn the typical filters that can extract features to represent image patches effectively. This deep network has been trained to extract the hierarchical features from each patch. This deep learning approach provides an improvement in image registration with high level features.

Finding the appropriate feature representation of an image is the most essential task in classification problem. Nowadays, quite a lot of supervised and unsupervised learning models are available to find the right feature representation for the target application. The best feature representation always leads to fast network convergence and minimum classification error. Deep Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) [4] has the ability to learn the best feature representation of the input image automatically. The performance of deep CNN is directly related to the

volume of data used for training the network. Usually the medical fields are lacking in labelled datasets especially for lung cancer.

Moreover, training the deep CNN from scratch with a smaller amount data leads to over fitting and increases the computational load. This can be overcome by transfer learning [5], this transfers the learning between similar tasks and modify the learned model to the target domain.

Krizhevsky et al. [6] have developed a deep CNN with eight convolution layers for image classification and this is ranked among the top five error rate classification algorithms in 2012 imagenet competition. Anthimopoulos et al. [7] have proposed a nine-layer deep CNN to classify the interstitial lung diseases. Many researchers have reported that the deep learning algorithms [8, 9] are adapted to the field of clinical diagnosis with medical images. Mohanty et al. [8] have demonstrated that the transfer learning improves the accuracy of classification system with less execution time.

Many deep learning based approaches have been developed on image classification with improved accuracy, but these deep CNN models are not able to produce the similar performance on lung cancer detection. In this paper, different fine-tuned VGG16 models based on transfer learning approach has been developed for lung cancer detection system which classifies the CT images into three broad categories such as normal, primary lung cancer and metastatic lung cancer. These models are established on top of the pre-trained VGG16 model. These models utilize the pre-trained VGG16 for low level feature extraction, further it learns the domain specific features by fine-tuning the model.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 explains the various procedures followed in developing the automated lung cancer detection system. Section 3 provides the detail discussion on the experiment results and quantitative analysis. Section 4 concludes the work and discusses the challenges for future research.

II. Methodology

Pre-processing

In order to improve the result of lung cancer detection system, the input data is processed and prepared for the network. At first, the input image is normalized to zero mean and unit variance. Since the images are captured with different scanners, contrast normalization is required to avoid the effect of illuminations. The contrast of image is adjusted to have a sharp difference between pixels. Deep learning approach provides better results when the model is trained with large datasets [10]. Therefore, the size of the dataset is amplified through data augmentation [11]. Data augmentation is the popular technique, which enlarge the dataset size by multiple times. Also, this prevents the model from trapping into over fitting issue and helps to build a generalized model. The dataset is augmented by applying geometric transformations to the existing image with keras Image Data Generator.

Deep Convolutional Neural Network

The advancements in deep convolutional neural network enable end-to-end medical image classification. Deep CNN is an artificial neural network, which categorize the image automatically in a supervised fashion. Typical CNN model has a set of convolutional layers with activation function, pooling layers and followed by dense (fully connected) layers. At convolution layer the weights are shared so that the number of trainable parameters are reduced which prevents the network from over fitting. The convolutional layers are using nonlinear activation function for retaining the essential properties. Different filters are applied at various levels of convolutional layer for extracting different level of features. Pooling layer is used to reduce the dimension of the data by avoiding the repeated data. The network is ended with a dense layer with softmax activation function, which yields the classification results. The trainable parameters of the deep CNN are adjusted repeatedly with back propagation technique. The network parameters in every iteration are adjusted using gradient descent optimization method. In the recent years, a numerous amount of deep CNN networks have been developed for image classification. But these deep networks are not appropriate for classifying the medical images on small dataset. In order to increase the performance of the existing deep CNN models on medical images, transfer learning is applied and then the model is adjusted to the target domain. The ability of VGG16 in classifying the lung cancer images with various transfer learning approach is analyzed in the section 3.

SVM-L2 on Top of Pre-trained VGG16 Model

The Visual Geometry Group (VGG) has developed a deep convolutional network is called as VGG16. This VGG16 has achieved better result on object recognition in a huge imagenet database. VGG16 model has totally 16 layers including 13 convolution layers followed by three fully connected layers. The convolution layers extract representative features from the input image with 3x3 size of convolution filters. The work process of fully

connected layer is similar to multilayer perceptron model. The images are classified into different categories based on the extracted features by the last fully connected layer. VGG16 uses the fully connected layer with softmax activation function for multiclass classification. Most of the existing image classification algorithms use the supervised classifier called Support vector machine for multiclass classification. SVM-L2 [12] is a special type of SVM classifier that minimizes the squared hinge loss. In order to train the CNN with respect to SVM's objective, the softmax layer is replaced by SVM-L2 for improving the performance of lung cancer detection system. The architecture of the pre-trained model with SVM-L2 is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Architecture of Pre-trained VGG16 Model with SVM-L2 Classifier

Training Procedure

- Step 1: The VGG16 pre-trained model is kept as non-trainable model and used to extract the features from the input image.
- Step 2: SVM-L2 classifier is attached on the top of this pre-trained model. It receives the features which are extracted from the pre-trained model and learns to classify the image.
- Step 3: Repeat the training process (step 2) until all the images are classified correctly otherwise the stopping condition is reached.

Transfer Learning and Fine-tuning

Transfer learning is the most popular machine learning technique, where the model trained for one domain is adapted to another domain. The model can be used without adjustments provided that the two application domains are related, otherwise the model has to be fine-tuned to the target domain. The pre-trained model VGG16 is trained on imagenet dataset where the model is used to classify heterogeneous images. Here the model is adjusted to classify the chest CT scan images with nodules into three classes. The CT images are homogeneous in nature, so adapting the pre-trained model into the target domain is a challenging task. Various possible models with VGG16 are experimented in detecting the lung cancer and all the experimented models are illustrated in the Fig. 2. In general, the earlier convolutional layers of the deep CNN extract the standard features like edges, strokes, etc..., which are commonly used in image classification tasks. Whereas the later layers are more specific to the domain in which the network is trained. In order to adapt the network for lung cancer detection, the network is trained with the following training procedure.

Fig. 2: Architecture of Fine-tuned VGG16 Model for Lung Cancer Detection

Training Procedure

- Step 1: Transfer the learning from VGG16 to the deep CNN for lung cancer detection. The deep CNN model is initialized with pre-trained VGG16 weights.

- Step 2: Freeze the weights and bias parameters of the earlier convolutional layers. The earlier layers are kept as non-trainable and the rest of the layers are left as trainable.
- Step 3: Fine tuning the trainable layers of the network,
- During forward pass, the network broadcasts the training data and compute the output at every layer using its activation function. At the output layer the error is computed by comparing the obtained output and actual output.
 - Propagate the error back through the network and update the weights of the unfrozen layers using Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) algorithm.
 - Repeat the steps 3.a and 3.b for each data in the training dataset.
- Step 4: Repeat the fine tuning process until all the data are classified correctly otherwise the stopping condition is reached.

III. Experimental setup

Datasets

LIDC-IRDI [13-15] is a publically available dataset which consists of thoracic Computed Tomography (CT) scans of 1018 cases collected from seven institutions. Each case is examined manually by four experienced radiologists and the diagnosis details are given in XML format. Based on the diagnosis results, the cases are broadly categorized into three groups: Normal, Primary lung cancer and Meta static cancer. Sample CT scan images taken from LIDC-IRDI are shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: Sample CT Scan Images taken from LIDC-IRDI Dataset

Training Configuration

All deep CNN networks are trained using SGD optimizer [16] with the fixed momentum of 0.9 and the learning rate of 0.00001. All these networks are trained for maximum of 50 epochs on the LIDC-IRDI dataset with a mini batch size of 10. Accuracy is used as a metric to fit the network during training. The data set is divided into training and validation set with 80-20 split. For every epoch the training and validation data has been shuffled in order to minimize the network over fitting. (No. of inputs)

Performance Evaluation

The performance of the various deep CNN models are tested with 90 new images randomly taken from LIDC-IRDI dataset. Every image can be classified either correctly or incorrectly, therefore the classification results can fall under four cases: true positive (TP), false negative (FN), true negative (TN), and false positive (FP). If an image is classified correctly, it is defined as TP, otherwise, it is taken as FN. Also, if the image is rejected correctly, it is defined as TN, otherwise it is taken as FP. The performance of the deep CNN models are evaluated using precision, recall, *f*-measure and accuracy which are calculated according to the equations (1), (2), (3) and (4) respectively.

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (1)$$

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (2)$$

$$f - measure = \frac{2 * Recall * Precision}{Precision + Recall} \quad (3)$$

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + FN + TN + FP} \quad (4)$$

IV. Results and Discussion

The lung cancer detection system based on transfer learning is implemented to classify the normal, primary lung cancer and metastatic lung cancer patients using thoracic CT scans. The deep convolutional model is trained with thousand two hundred low dose chest CT scan images from LIDC-IRDI dataset with pulmonary nodules. The imbalance training dataset severely affects the training process, therefore the images are selected randomly using stratified sampling technique. This selection method ensures that the samples are selected evenly from all the three categories such as normal case, primary lung cancer and metastatic lung cancer. The training and validation accuracy of the fine-tuned VGG16 model with first three frozen blocks obtained during training phase is plotted in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4: Training and Validation Accuracy Curves on LIDC-IRDI Dataset

From Fig. 4, it is observed that the training and validation results have similar convergence rate for the fine-tuned VGG16 model with first three frozen blocks. This conforms that the proposed deep CNN model does not trap into overfitting problem. It is also observed that the accuracy of the deep network is improved when the network is initialized with pre-trained model weights. The fine-tuned model is evaluated with 300 samples of 100 in each category. The performance of various deep CNN models such as trained from scratch, SVM on top of pre-trained VGG16 and fine-tuned VGG16 are compared on lung cancer detection. The experimental results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Results of Accuracy, Precision, Recall and *f*-score for Different VGG16 Model on LIDC-IRDI Database

Model	Class	Precision	Recall	<i>f</i> -measure
Pre-trained VGG16 (block1-5 are frozen)	Normal	0.78	0.70	0.74
	Primary Lung Cancer	1.00	0.70	0.82
	Meta Static Lung cancer	0.64	0.90	0.75
	Average	0.81	0.77	0.77
Fine-tuned VGG16 (block1-4 are frozen)	Normal	0.76	0.74	0.75
	Primary Lung Cancer	0.74	0.81	0.78
	Meta Static Lung cancer	0.89	0.83	0.86
	Average	0.80	0.79	0.79
Fine-tuned VGG16 (block1-3 are frozen)	Normal	0.97	0.86	0.91
	Primary Lung Cancer	0.89	1.00	0.94
	Meta Static Lung cancer	0.96	0.95	0.95
	Average	0.94	0.94	0.94
Fine-tuned VGG16 (block1-2 are frozen)	Normal	0.87	0.96	0.91
	Primary Lung Cancer	0.89	0.87	0.88
	Meta Static Lung cancer	0.95	0.87	0.91
	Average	0.90	0.90	0.90
Fine-tuned VGG16 (pre-trained weights)	Normal	0.82	0.89	0.85
	Primary Lung Cancer	0.82	0.92	0.86
	Meta Static Lung cancer	0.99	0.79	0.88
	Average	0.87	0.86	0.86
Fine-tuned VGG16 (random weights)	Normal	0.87	0.93	0.90
	Primary Lung Cancer	0.86	0.95	0.90
	Meta Static Lung cancer	0.96	0.80	0.87
	Average	0.90	0.89	0.89
Pre-trained VGG16 + SVM-L2	Normal	0.70	0.40	0.49
	Primary Lung Cancer	0.60	0.40	0.47
	Meta Static Lung cancer	0.49	0.80	0.59
	Average	0.60	0.53	0.51

From the obtained results, it is clear that the fine-tuned VGG16 model with first three frozen blocks performs better than other fine-tuned models. VGG16 model has been trained on huge dataset imagenet for classifying 1000 categories of images. As a result the earlier layers of VGG16 extracts the common low level features for image classification. But the later layer extracts the high level features which are highly correlated to the target application. In this work the features learned innatural image classification are transferred to medical image classification. Since the learning is transferred between heterogeneous tasks, features need to be adjusted slowly to the target domain. In order to classify the chest CT images in LIDC-IRDI dataset,the model is retrained with slow learning rate. The classification accuracy obtained by the various fine-tuned models is plotted in Fig.5.

From the plot it is observed that, fine-tuning the whole model yields 86.33% accuracy. However fine-tuning only the later blocks achieves 4% improvement over whole model fine-tuning (VGG16 pre-trained weights) in terms of accuracy. Also it is noted that the fine-tuned VGG16 outperforms the VGG16 with SVM-L2 by 31% in terms of accuracy. Finally the experimental results conforms that the fine-tuned VGG16 model (Block 1-3 are frozen) outperforms other models in terms of accuracy, precision, recall and *f*-measure.

Fig. 5: Comparison of Classification Accuracies (%) Obtained by Different Fine-tuned VGG16 Models

V. Conclusion

The end-to-end deep CNN model has been developed to detect the lung cancer from low dose chest CT scan image. The proposed deep CNN utilizes the weights of the pre-trained VGG16 model to extract the low level representative features at the earlier layers and learn the high level domain specific features with low learning rate. The experimental results provethat the transfer learning improves the performance of lung cancer classification system. The proposed model produces more accurate results than the random training approaches. The fine-tuned deep CNN achieves improved performance than the deep CNN trained from scratch, which confirms that the transfer learning between different domains will improves the learning capacity of the network. Hence the proposed model results may possibly support the radiologist for accurate diagnoses.

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